

NAVIGATING THE CHALLENGES OF AI BIAS AND DISCRIMINATION

Mayank Malhotra*, Harshita Prasad**

*Student Researcher, Christ (Deemed to be university), Delhi NCR, India

**Student Researcher, Christ (Deemed to be university), Delhi NCR, India

ABSTRACT: *The advent of the twenty-first century has been accompanied by the fourth industrial revolution (Industries 4.0), propelled by artificial intelligence (AI). Each technology conglomerate, national government, and international institution is solely concerned with the optimal way to utilize and leverage the capabilities of artificial intelligence for the betterment of society and the economy this due to the exponential rate of technological advancement has given rise to artificial intelligence as a contemporary contentious issue. Numerous domains that have an impact on human existence have been influenced by artificial intelligence; conversely, its advancement has introduced an innumerable array of legal complexities. Artificial intelligence (AI) possesses immense potential to safeguard human rights. Nevertheless, it may also undermine human rights to some degree. Rascally discriminatory human rights violations have resulted from the use of AI-based surveillance, face detection, and other functions. AI experts have acknowledged the potential for biased AI inventions due to developer bias. The purpose of this research article is to examine the potential adverse effects of AI technology. Increasingly, machine learning decision-making systems are operating entirely autonomously, devoid of human judgment. Algorithms now possess final authority over life-altering situations. Employment opportunities, identification, security, public distribution, and criminal justice systems are all reliant on algorithmic decisions, regardless of the presence or absence of human judgment. Therefore, how does one imbue an immaterial, amoral entity with the principles of responsibility and accountability? The paper's author also wants to discuss how artificial intelligence affects gender equality, including the UN's role in promoting gender equality through conventions and resolutions, whether AI threatens gender equality and possible*

countermeasures. The paper will also compare AI laws in India and internationally to determine how to regulate AI use with these emerging technologies.

KEYWORDS: Biased, responsibility and accountability, gender equality, AI (Artificial Intelligence).

INTRODUCTION

After more than fifty years since its inception, artificial intelligence (AI) is currently popular. AI technologies play a significant role in shaping the information we see on social media, evaluating the risks of defendants in criminal cases, determining the creditworthiness of individuals, and even recommending the best way to get home from work.

Many AI systems are trained on past data, enabling them to identify trends, learn from examples, and make predictions for decision-making. These forecasts and categorizations are broad observations derived from extensive datasets that would be challenging for humans to analyze as quickly and co

The influence of AI is considered to be so revolutionary that it has been compared to 'new electricity'. As industry and governments advance in developing and deploying these technologies, attention has also turned to their societal and ethical implications.

Despite its increasing influence in various areas of our lives, there is no universally agreed-upon definition of "artificial intelligence." It encompasses a range of computational methods and processes aimed at enhancing machines' capacity to perform tasks that demand intelligence, like pattern recognition, computer vision, and language processing. Given the broad interpretation and the fast evolution of technology, it's not unexpected that the definition of artificial intelligence evolves. This phenomenon is commonly referred to as the "AI effect" or the "odd paradox": once groundbreaking advancements eventually become ordinary and routine, they are no longer considered AI, while newer technologies with enhanced capabilities are now classified as AI.¹

¹ Ahmet EFE, The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Social Problems and Solutions: An Analysis on The Context of Digital Divide and Exploitation, <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/yenimedya/issue/73764/1146586>.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming more prevalent in various aspects of our society, ranging from important fields like healthcare and humanitarian aid to everyday activities like dating. AI, such as embodied AI in robotics and methods like machine learning, has the potential to improve economic, and social welfare, and the protection of human rights. The different industries listed can gain advantages from these new technologies. Simultaneously, AI could be misused or exhibit unexpected and potentially harmful behaviors. Discussions about the impact of regulations, ethical considerations, and technological advancements on governing AI systems are now more important than ever. According to Floridi, the digital revolution is reshaping our perspectives on values, ethics, and sustainable innovation, making governance a critical concern.

Thus, AI has become a powerful technology, greatly impacting different parts of our society and playing a major role in our daily lives, work, and relationships. It is essential to explore the potential effects of AI on human rights, especially on vulnerable groups such as women, children, persons with disabilities, and racial and ethnic minorities, as we navigate the evolving technological environment. This report aims to present findings and analysis that illuminate the implications of AI on human rights and investigate how current human rights norms and frameworks can regulate its impact effectively.²

In recent years, the AI industry has faced significant challenges. AI, instead of being an impartial and objective tool that can help create a just and equitable society, has been proven to do the opposite.

It perpetuates and even amplifies existing structural biases in society and works favorably in maintaining power balances in society. Given the uncertain socio-political environment in India, it is crucial to have human oversight when implementing these AI decision-making models. Regulatory measures and policy interventions are crucial at this time.

AI is a sophisticated social system that should not be judged solely on accuracy and efficiency. This paper will recognise the importance of the policy sector stepping in to oversee and control the AI sector to safeguard fundamental rights. Finally, suggestions will be offered for a thorough

²Irene Kitsara, Artificial Intelligence and the Digital Divide: From an Innovation Perspective, SpringerLink (Mar. 29, 2022), https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-90192-9_12.

national policy on ethical AI decision-making models that establish a responsible and accountable framework.³

Research Problem

1. *How can we develop and deploy AI systems that are fair, accountable, and transparent, minimizing the potential for bias and discrimination?*
2. *How can we leverage the benefits of AI while mitigating its risks to ensure the protection of human rights, especially for vulnerable populations?*

Literature review

1. Gender bias perpetuation and mitigation in AI technologies: challenges and opportunities - by Sinead O'Connor · Helen Liu

The study examines gender inequalities in AI systems and emphasises the need for collaboration between technology, gender studies, and public policy researchers. It shows how AI may reinforce human prejudice and how it might mitigate it. The research divides AI technology by text or picture input and gives case examples that combine technological and sociological bias assessment methods. The conclusion suggests researchers collaborate to study algorithmic responsibility and AI's possible effects. The paper addresses how technologies reflect their designers' unconscious prejudices and obtain new meanings and biases via repeated usage, possibly impacting policy and employment choices. It stresses the necessity for extensive investigations on technological, social, and policy impacts of gender bias in AI technologies. The research also recommends regulatory changes to control AI and reduce gender biases, reflecting the growing number of concerns that must be addressed.⁴

³Digital technologies and human rights: challenges and opportunities, <https://www.amazoniainvestiga.info/index.php/amazonia/article/view/2607>.

⁴Gender bias perpetuation and mitigation in AI technologies: challenges and opportunities, Springerprofessional.De <https://www.springerprofessional.de/en/gender-bias-perpetuation-and-mitigation-in-ai-technologies-chall/25338510>.

2. ACCOUNTABILITY and RESPONSIBILITY of ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DECISION-MAKING MODELS in INDIAN POLICY LANDSCAPE - by Palak Malhotra , Amita Misra

The document is a research report that highlights the importance of establishing a thorough national policy in the Indian context regarding ethical AI decision-making models to establish a responsible and accountable framework. The text delves into the difficulties of assigning responsibility and accountability to autonomous machine learning decision-making systems, the ethical dilemma of bias in AI decision-making models, and how organisations avoid taking responsibility and being held accountable. The report emphasises the importance of policy intervention and regulation to safeguard fundamental rights and offers suggestions for developing a thorough national policy on ethical AI decision-making models.⁵

3. Artificial intelligence policy in India: a framework for engaging the limits of data-driven decision-making - by Vidushi Marda

The document is a research report titled "Artificial intelligence policy in India: a framework for engaging the limits of data-driven decision-making" by Vidushi Marda, published in 2018. The document outlines a structure for evaluating the constraints and potential dangers of data-based decision-making in AI projects, with a specific emphasis on the key phases involved in implementing machine learning: data collection, model development, and application deployment. The report examines India's current AI policy landscape and utilises the proposed framework to address ongoing sectoral challenges in India, with the goal of impacting existing policy discussions in the country⁶

Research Objectives

- 1. Promote public confidence and openness in AI systems.*
- 2. Explore and create AI algorithms that prioritize fairness and are more resistant to bias.*

⁵ ACCOUNTABILITY and RESPONSIBILITY of ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DECISION-MAKING MODELS in INDIAN POLICY LANDSCAPE, (June 25, 2022), <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3215/5.pdf>

⁶ Marda, Vidushi, Artificial Intelligence Policy in India: A Framework for Engaging the Limits of Data-Driven Decision-Making (August 29, 2018). Philosophical Transactions A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences (2018) , Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3240384> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3240384>

3. *Human-AI Collaboration and Responsible Deployment Examining the influence of AI on particular rights such as privacy, freedom of expression, and non-discrimination.*
4. *Identifying groups that are particularly impacted by AI risks, such as refugees, minorities, and individuals with disabilities.*

Research question

- How can we create, build, and implement AI systems that reduce bias and discrimination, especially towards vulnerable populations, while maximizing the societal advantages of this technology?

Methodology

The methodology utilized in order to carry out research is purely doctrinal in nature. This paper solely relies on doctrinal methods such as books, papers and primary sources like organizational reports and surveys were among the many places that data came from. Thus, this study is entirely theoretical and interpretive in nature.

Hypothesis

By utilizing a comprehensive strategy that emphasizes fairness in data, design of algorithms, human supervision, and inclusive development methods, we can greatly diminish prejudice and unfair treatment in AI systems, resulting in fairer results, especially for marginalized groups.

1. Charting the Course: India's AI Policy Takes Flight

India's AI policy landscape is like a rapidly developing airport - bustling with activity but still under construction.

1.1. Artificial intelligence as a rapidly growing focus area

Emphasizing the importance of AI, the Indian Government has been actively focusing on its development, adoption, and promotion, believing that AI can improve lives and promote equality in society. In 2018, the Union government allocated a significant amount of funding towards research, training, and skilling in emerging technologies such as AI, marking a 100% increase from previous investment.⁷

⁷Prasanth Nair, AI in governance — there's nothing artificial about it, (May 10, 2023), <https://www.deccanherald.com/opinion/ai-in-governance-there-s-nothing-artificial-about-it-1217401.html>.

1.2. Government Takeoff: Embracing the Potential of AI

Emphasizing digital technology has been a longstanding practice. The government's Digital India initiative aims to transform India into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. Digital India aims to offer digital infrastructure as a fundamental utility to all citizens, integrating digitization into governance, and ultimately empowering the population. Funding for research, training, and skilling in emerging technologies like AI is being allocated as part of the Digital India programme. The government has also started efforts to ensure that AI technology is developed in India and tailored to benefit the country, aligning with its Make In India programme, which aims to boost India's position as a global manufacturing center.

AI has been a significant focus in digital technologies, with several initiatives dedicated specifically to AI. This section will provide an examination of specific notable aspects of each initiative discussed in this article, without aiming to be a comprehensive analysis of each.

The Indian government has shown a proactive approach in promoting AI development. Efforts such as the INDIAai platform and the national AI portal showcase a dedicated focus on utilizing AI's capabilities for economic advancement and societal development. These platforms act as central hubs for promoting research, collaboration, and knowledge sharing within the AI ecosystem. Moreover, government funding programmes assist research institutions and startups creating cutting-edge AI solutions in different industries.⁸

1.3. Guiding through Ethical Airspace: Dealing with Bias and Discrimination

India is actively promoting AI development while also emphasizing the importance of responsible AI use. Moral issues related to AI, especially bias and discrimination, are becoming increasingly important. Recent reports by prominent organizations such as INDIA and NASSCOM emphasize the importance of strong frameworks to address these risks. These reports bring up important concerns regarding data privacy, fairness in algorithms, and the potential effects of AI on vulnerable groups.

⁸Niklas Berglind, The potential value of AI—and how governments could look to capture it, McKinsey (July 25, 2022), <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/public-sector/our-insights/the-potential-value-of-ai-and-how-governments-could-look-to-capture-it>.

1.4. Industry-Specific Regulations: Gradually Gaining Momentum

India's current strategy for regulating AI is marked by a sector-specific approach. Although there are no universal regulations for AI, laws in specific sectors are being modified to cover AI use within those areas. For example, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) has released guidelines regarding the implementation of AI in the financial industry, with the goal of promoting responsible innovation and reducing possible risks. Likewise, other governing bodies are expected to do the same, adjusting their structures to tackle AI-related obstacles within their respective domains.

1.5. Decentralised Control Tower: A Call for Collaboration

One of the current challenges in India's AI policy landscape is the scattered regulatory environment. At present, there is no unified authority monitoring AI advancement in all industries. Various ministries and agencies oversee different aspects of AI, including data privacy, ethical considerations, and sectoral applications. This decentralized approach, although it provides certain benefits in terms of flexibility, may result in coordination challenges and regulatory inconsistencies. For a strong and efficient regulatory framework, it's essential to work together with key stakeholders from government, industry, and academia.

1.6. The Flight Path Forward: A Collaborative Approach

India's AI policy landscape is still in the early stages, but the foundation has been set for a promising journey ahead. With the government's strong backing and an increasing focus on ethical concerns, India is well-equipped to harness AI in a responsible manner. Looking ahead, cooperation is essential. Creating a central coordinating body or a national strategy for AI could simplify regulatory procedures and guarantee a uniform approach across different industries. Moreover, promoting public conversation and involving various stakeholders in policy talks will be essential in establishing trust and guaranteeing AI meets the requirements of all individuals.

Finally, India's AI policy landscape is beginning to soar. Despite facing obstacles, the nation has the opportunity to establish itself as a frontrunner in ethical AI advancement and implementation. India can successfully address the ethical and regulatory challenges

of this powerful technology through collaboration, ensuring that AI benefits society and promotes a more inclusive, equitable future.⁹

2. AI on Trial: The Ethical Tightrope of Biased Decisions

Artificial intelligence (AI) is quickly changing our world, with the potential to completely transform various sectors such as healthcare diagnostics and financial services. Nevertheless, a crucial issue hides within this potent technology: prejudice. Similar to how a judge handles a complicated legal case, we need to thoughtfully examine the ethical balancing act of AI decision-making, as bias can result in unjust and prejudiced results.

Picture a scenario in a courtroom where AI models are on trial for their decisions. Is there any incriminating evidence? Prejudice is ingrained in the algorithms that dictate their behavior. AI models are trained on extensive datasets, which may inadvertently mirror the societal biases found in the real world. An AI recruitment tool trained on historical resumes that favor one gender might unknowingly perpetuate bias, unfairly disadvantaging qualified individuals. Here is a prime illustration of how prejudice can seep into AI systems, resulting in unfair results in loan approvals, risk assessments, and the criminal justice system. Here, bias' potential effects are clear: financial exclusion for particular demographics or unfair targeting by the justice system.

The ethical considerations surrounding bias in AI go well beyond simple technical errors. It compels us to address fundamental questions about fairness, accountability, and transparency. Who bears the responsibility for a biased AI decision—the programmers, the companies implementing the technology, or the data used to train the models? How can we guarantee openness in these intricate algorithms where the decision-making process might be concealed in layers of code? These are important questions that policymakers, developers, and society as a whole must address.

Thankfully, AI has an opportunity for defence. Researchers are currently investigating methods to reduce bias in AI. This involves creating methods to detect and eliminate bias from training data, an essential initial move to guarantee more equitable results. Furthermore, researchers are

⁹ Daniel Varona, Discrimination, Bias, Fairness, and Trustworthy AI, Discrimination, Bias, Fairness, and Trustworthy AI <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/12/12/5826>.

developing algorithms with equity as a priority, integrating restrictions or goals that encourage impartial decision-making. Incorporating human oversight mechanisms is another crucial strategy. People have the ability to assess important AI results and step in if needed, serving as a protection against unfair judgements.

In addition to technical solutions, it is crucial to promote diversity within AI development teams. Diverse teams are more effective at recognising and dealing with possible biases in technology. Discussion on ethical AI in the public sphere is another critical aspect. By openly discussing the challenges and potential solutions, we can create a system that benefits everyone, not just a select few.

Ultimately, AI has the capacity to greatly enhance our daily experiences. Yet, the possibility of prejudice jeopardizes the advancements made. Recognising the ethical challenges of biased AI and proactively finding solutions can guarantee a just trial for this technology. Now is the time for action. Let's utilize AI to advance fairness, inclusivity, and a more equitable future in a world influenced by algorithms.¹⁰

2.1. Can AI ultimately benefit everyone?

Many policy documents, international conventions, and tech giants promote AI with the vision of benefiting society as a whole. They highlight the benefits of artificial intelligence and the economic growth it will bring to the country, promoting human well-being. Computer scientists and tech companies frequently portray algorithms as being purely logical things. They are considered to be logical concerns based on mathematics and technology. On the surface, an impartial and logical algorithm making important decisions like resume screening, parole determination, and medical diagnosis is seen as a significant advancement. It is seen as a fair and impartial decision-making system that aims to eliminate any existing biases present in human judgement and power dynamics in society. It will ignite human growth and success. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that AI's decision-making system can bring about positive outcomes and enhance quality of life, but it can also uphold the existing societal structure. The current research on machine learning applications has emphasized how these

¹⁰ Cath Corinne 2018Governing artificial intelligence: ethical, legal and technical opportunities and challengesPhil. Trans. R. Soc. A.3762018008020180080

algorithms can worsen inequalities in societies and even strengthen them. Therefore, it is a practical viewpoint to think that AI will support human development.

2.2. AI perpetuates societal bias.

A bias is an inclination or prejudice for or against one person or a group, particularly in a manner deemed unfair, according to the lexicon definition. When unfair and false judgements are made due to pre-existing discriminatory stereotypes about certain groups, bias becomes evident. These judgements are often irrelevant to the actual situation. Algorithms for making decisions using machine learning or artificial intelligence (AI) may have biases against weaker and marginalized groups in society. The ethical issue of generating a partial decision by an AI learning algorithm is linked to the unpredictability of the outcome, known as the ‘Black-Box Problem’. Learning algorithms are given a historical dataset to learn from to solve a specific problem or complete a task. However, these learning algorithms do not receive any right or wrong answers to the problem statement. They base their decisions on their inclinations, identifying patterns and relationships among various factors. For example, in a resume screening algorithm, the algorithm will be provided with a training data set of the resumes of their top-performing employees in the company. Following that, the algorithm is responsible for identifying patterns or connections present in all these resumes, ultimately making them the most successful resumes. The benchmark that the algorithm uses to pass the screening test for potential candidates is these correlations or similarities. This helps reduce the need for additional human effort and expenses. Nevertheless, human judgement is entirely removed from it. Neither the person implementing the system nor the individual using it can accurately predict what the algorithm will glean from the data provided. Thus, the process of acquiring information, analyzing it, and reaching conclusions happens within a closed system. This can be particularly concerning when the developer inputs a dataset that is filled with bias into the system. Consider the example of the resume screening algorithm and how it could perpetuate and reinforce an existing societal bias. If a company has a track record of favoring certain demographics in hiring, there will be a lack of resumes from underrepresented groups in datasets.¹¹

¹¹Emilio Ferrara, Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Brief Survey of Sources, Impacts, and Mitigation Strategies, Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Br <https://www.mdpi.com/2413-4155/6/1/3>.

The system, without considering the disparities in structure, could infer from the data that resumes of female or black candidates are subpar. It sees fewer black or female candidates' resumes as a reflection of their actual performance and cognitive abilities, rather than societal inequalities. Hence, despite the minority community being qualified and potentially an excellent candidate, the algorithm overlooks the resume or relegates it to secondary consideration based on gender or race.

Unfair and unjust biases have infiltrated criminal justice systems, healthcare access, and intelligence-led policing.

2.3. AI exacerbates inequality in India.

Two national policies are influencing India's AI strategy. The Indian government has increased funding for AI technology research, training, and skill development as part of the Digital India initiative. AI applications play a crucial role in various government initiatives such as the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana, Smart Cities, E-Pathshala, E-Prison, E-Farmers Portal, and E-Courts as part of the Digital India Mission. In India, the government is encouraging domestic investments and technologies through the Make in India programme. The Ministry of Commerce and Industry set up an AI Task Force to tackle socio-economic challenges in national security, agriculture, education, smart cities, finance, and manufacturing. While the legal and regulatory framework in India is praised for accommodating the swift integration of AI, it falls short of addressing the ethical dilemmas that arise.¹²

Unfair biases have infiltrated Indian criminal justice, healthcare, and intelligence-led policing. Historical dataset bias is the primary reason for such biased results. For instance, law enforcement agencies utilize data-driven algorithms to pinpoint criminal hotspots by analyzing neighborhoods with the highest number of arrests for crimes. This poses a significant issue in countries like India, where law enforcement often conducts arrests without proper cause. In India, law enforcement frequently categorizes criminals and neighborhoods according to religion and caste. Mainly marginalized caste and religious groups will be singled out in biased data. Unfair detentions could be a consequence of an excessive police presence in the area. Only

¹² Artificial Intelligence, the Future of Work, and Inequality, Magazine
<https://magazine.libarts.colostate.edu/article/artificial-intelligence-the-future-of-work-and-inequality/>.

additional training data is utilized from these arrests. AI algorithms perpetuate and exacerbate bias. This problem is apparent in Delhi's CMPAS, reinforcing police biases based on caste and religion.

- Violating minority rights and facing discrimination can have severe consequences for the well-being and freedoms of marginalized groups. Nevertheless, the government has not confirmed these patterns.

A dataset can be biased even without historical biases due to inefficiencies resulting from inadequate datasets. Some indications are that the face recognition algorithms utilized by law enforcement and businesses could worsen systemic biases related to race and gender. There is a lack of representation from various social backgrounds in databases. Even though facial recognition systems boast a 90% accuracy rate, they are not widespread. Disadvantaged social groups continue to experience a higher error rate. Several studies indicate that facial recognition software utilized in surveillance, airport screening, and employment/housing decisions may misidentify non-white, non-male, and Asian individuals at significantly higher rates compared to white faces. This programme has a higher error rate for incorrectly identifying women compared to men. Moreover, automated gender classification suggests a fixed concept that remains consistent across different periods and cultures. Even though AI biases have been studied in Western countries, they have not been investigated in India. Considering the existing power dynamics in the Indian state, AI decision-making models could potentially strengthen the current inequalities. AI decision-making tools are set to automate eligibility and entitlement determinations for Indian citizens regarding opportunities and social benefits.

It might violate Indian constitutional rights related to due process and freedom from discrimination. There are currently no laws or regulations in India that specifically deal with biases in AI decision-making systems and how to prevent or reduce them. The only current project is NITI Aayog's National Strategy on Artificial Intelligence (NSAI), to create a

framework for responsible and accountable AI to prevent harm from AI decision-making models.¹³

3. AI: A Boon or Bane for Human Rights?

Artificial Intelligence is not being created in a vacuum or applied to an empty space. Instead, certain social actors are using AI to automate decision-making in certain industries. They're acting in this manner to accomplish goals they consider desirable in the context of societal structures that already have human rights consequences of their own.

Take into consideration, for instance, the use of AI in the criminal justice system, which is covered in further detail in the first case study that follows. judicial defendants have been granted a number of rights during the past few centuries in order to guarantee the impartiality of judicial trials. These include, among many others, the right to a fair trial, the assumption of innocence, the legality principle, and many others. Nevertheless, no criminal justice system in place fully respects the rights of defendants and other pertinent rights-holders; all such systems have some detrimental effects on rights-holders who existed before artificial intelligence was invented.¹⁴

The only way we can truly comprehend the effects of integrating AI into the criminal justice system—or any other human institution—on human rights is to adopt a comparative approach that takes into consideration pre-AI baseline conditions. The human rights effects of adding AI will be confused with the continued effects of whatever was there previously unless the human rights implications—both good and negative—of pre-existing institutional frameworks are recognised and taken into consideration. Here, we provide a two-step process for averting these problems.¹⁵

¹³ Laurence Brooks, Ensuring a 'Responsible' AI future in India: RRI as an approach for identifying the ethical challenges from an Indian perspective, *AI and Ethics* (Dec. 19, 2023), <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43681-023-00370-w>.

¹⁴ Bishal Bose, Artificial Intelligence: A Boon or Curse ? - Bishal Bose, *Medium* (Jan. 12, 2023), <https://bishalbose294.medium.com/artificial-intelligence-a-boon-or-curse-8915dcef5f14>.

¹⁵ Rebecca Walker, Is AI a Boon or a Bane?, *Coruzant Technologies* (Jan. 26, 2023), <https://coruzant.com/ai/is-ai-a-boon-or-a-bane/>.

3.1. The Diverse Human Rights Effects of AI

The advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers a future of unmatched convenience and effectiveness. Nevertheless, this impressive advancement looms large over the realm of human rights. The influence of AI spans different fundamental rights, requiring a thorough assessment of its possible advantages and drawbacks.

One of the most alarming problems is the possibility of discrimination ingrained in AI systems. Algorithms trained on skewed data can reinforce current disparities in loan approvals, criminal justice, and job recruitment. Picture a scenario where a loan approval system unintentionally favours certain ethnicities, resulting in financial exclusion. Likewise, a risk assessment tool utilised in criminal justice may unjustly focus on particular demographics, prompting significant worries about impartial trials and equitable treatment.¹⁶

Privacy rights are also being closely examined in the era of AI. As AI systems gather and analyse large amounts of personal data, the risk of misuse and surveillance becomes a significant concern. Picture a scenario where facial recognition technology monitors our every action, establishing an eerie environment of continuous surveillance. These situations underscore the importance of strong data protection regulations to protect personal privacy in a world driven by data.

Moreover, AI algorithms could potentially hinder freedom of expression by censoring content. Authorities or companies could use AI to stifle opposition or manipulate information, violating people's freedom to voice their thoughts. Moreover, the emergence of "deepfakes" – lifelike AI-generated videos or audio recordings – presents a challenge to our capacity to differentiate reality from falsehood, potentially weakening confidence in information and weakening the pillars of a free press.

Nevertheless, AI also has the potential to enhance human rights. Picture AI-driven technology being utilised to identify illnesses in underserved regions, enhancing healthcare availability for disadvantaged populations. AI could be utilised to analyse extensive datasets and recognise

¹⁶Hannah Thinyane, *Towards a Human Rights-Based Approach to AI: Case Study of Apprise*, SpringerLink (July 14, 2020), https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-52014-4_3.

patterns of discrimination, aiding in breaking down systemic biases. Moreover, AI systems can be trained to identify and alert about hate speech online, promoting a more welcoming and courteous digital atmosphere.

Ultimately, the influence of AI on human rights is complex. Through actively addressing bias, protecting privacy, and promoting transparency in AI development, we can unlock its potential to advance equality and well-being. Successfully managing the ethical challenges of AI involves a joint effort among governments, developers, and civil society. Only then can we guarantee that AI acts as a positive influence, protecting essential rights in the digital era.¹⁷

Utilizing the two-step framework from the previous section, we will now examine the extensive human rights implications of implementing AI decision-making in six areas:

- Criminal Justice (risk assessments)
- Finance (credit scores)
- Medical services (diagnostics)
- Content moderation (standards enforcement)
- Human Resources (recruitment and hiring)
- Academic Assessment (essay grading)

We selected these six fields from a wide range of options to showcase both the potential and challenges of this technology in various human rights aspects.

Furthermore, AI decision-making technologies are already being utilized in all of these areas, enabling our analysis to be based on current circumstances rather than hypothetical future advancements.

¹⁷ AI for humanitarian action: Human rights and ethics | International Review of the Red Cross, Cambridge Core (Mar. 1, 2021), <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/international-review-of-the-red-cross/article/abs/ai-for-humanitarian-action-human-rights-and-ethics/C91D044210CADF7A0E023862CF4EE758>.

When selecting these six use cases, we made a deliberate choice to exclude two AI applications that have sparked significant discussion and disagreement: self-driving vehicles and autonomous weapons systems. We have omitted these applications from our analysis as they have been more extensively researched compared to the use of AI in the other six fields we selected. In addition, the concerns regarding autonomous weapons systems are better addressed by international humanitarian law rather than international human rights law, as these systems are designed for use during conflicts.

While analyzing this, it became clear that every AI implementation could affect numerous rights through its direct and indirect consequences. To ensure clarity and analytical efficiency, our analysis has concentrated on the rights most affected by the deployment in question. This exercise involves drawing lines that are subjective by their very nature, but are essential to the approach advocated by the Guiding Principles for identifying human rights impacts so that they can be properly addressed.¹⁸

4. Recommendation for ensuring accountability and responsibility in AI

As mentioned earlier, the growing use of AI decision-making models in various sectors poses a significant risk to fundamental constitutional rights such as equality, freedom, and life liberty.¹⁹

Considering the unclear nature of responsibility and accountability in the realm of Artificial Intelligence, it is crucial for policy and governance to ensure that all stakeholders in the sociotechnical environment (researchers, developers, and managers) understand their obligations. The entire organization needs to be prepared to accept responsibility for any harm caused by bias or a potential flaw in the machine learning algorithm. NITI Aayog's NSAI and UNESCO's principles for AI have also recognized the importance of a responsible and accountable policy framework in developing an ethical AI decision-making system.²⁰

¹⁸A Human Rights-Based Approach to Responsible AI, (Oct. 6, 2022), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.02667>.

¹⁹ Mariarosaria Taddeo, Accountability in artificial intelligence: what it is and how it works, SpringerLink (Feb. 7, 2023), <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00146-023-01635-y>.

²⁰Jack Stevens, AI Accountability: Who's Responsible When AI Goes Wrong?, Emerge Digital (Aug. 4, 2023), <https://emerge.digital/resources/ai-accountability-whos-responsible-when-ai-goes-wrong/>.

4.1. Diverse Training of Staff

Individuals in STEM-related industries should receive instruction in fundamental social sciences to understand power dynamics, structural inequalities, and how technology can contribute to systemic oppression and marginalization of certain social groups. One way to accomplish this is by implementing a varied course curriculum and organizing mandatory awareness workshops in the workplace.

4.2. Understanding Algorithms and Transparency

As previously stated, AI algorithms operate in a 'black box construct' and their codes are kept confidential and proprietary. Moreover, there are specific intricacies related to the principle of transparency, like the lack of technical knowledge among the general population. Nevertheless, a nationwide ethical AI policy should promote a practical approach to requiring transparency to address the difficulties of technical literacy. Consider implementing provisions such as making algorithms more understandable to users, particularly in cases with potential social consequences, improving data literacy, and ensuring transparency in training data and algorithms.²¹

4.3. Consent with Full Knowledge

An ethical AI policy at a national level should require organisations to obtain informed consent from end-users. This consent should clearly outline that the services being used or any screening processes are automated. It's surprising that NITI Aayog's NSAI has not addressed issues of informed consent to end-users.²²

4.4. Embracing Diversity and Inclusion

Establishing a foundation for ethical AI begins with determining who has a voice in the decision-making process [7]. Promoting diversity and inclusivity is crucial in creating an ethical AI. It is important to embrace diversity in design [12]. Precision in datasets is crucial, as well as in AI-

²¹Virginia Dignum, The ART of AI — Accountability, Responsibility, Transparency, Medium (Mar. 4, 2018), <https://medium.com/@virginiadignum/the-art-of-ai-accountability-responsibility-transparency-48666ec92ea5>.

²²Ethics of Artificial Intelligence, UNESCO <https://www.unesco.org/en/artificial-intelligence/recommendation-ethics>.

focused research and development teams. Having a variety of employees results in enhanced decision-making and group dynamics, as researchers from different ethnic and gender backgrounds offer unique perspectives and the skills to challenge established ideas within a uniform group. It is important to consider diversity in design through incentive schemes, but certain groups like children and persons with disabilities may be overlooked. Hence, it is essential to involve a comprehensive group of stakeholders with extensive technical knowledge. These stakeholders will consist of subject matter experts and end users, particularly from communities facing high vulnerability. National policy may require the creation of advisory or consultative bodies consisting of academia and civil society organizations. Having advisors can lend legitimacy to the models and help alleviate public concerns.²³

4.5. Organizational Responsibility and Accountability

According to NITI Aayog's NSAI, the national policy for ethical AI emphasizes accountability and responsibility with proportionate liability. Additionally, it is important to implement the 'human in the loop' principle, ensuring that decisions deemed high risk are confirmed by a human before any action is executed. This is already being put into practice in different industry sectors in India that utilise automated AI. The NSAI document strongly promotes the concept of 'Human in the loop'.²⁴

4.6. Independent Auditing and Certification

There needs to be a system in place for independent oversight conducted by an external and technically competent body.

They are required to establish regulations and adopt a risk-based approach towards it. It implies that AI systems with significant social impacts will face stricter scrutiny and regulations, whereas algorithms with minimal social consequences may have fewer requirements. An independent regulatory body will examine, confirm, and test AI-based algorithms, applications, and products against well-defined ethical principles. Moreover, the requirements for regulations can be approached from a risk-based perspective, leading to the certification of an algorithm.

²³ (Mar. 10, 2024), <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9905430/>.

²⁴ Artificial Intelligence and Ethical Accountability, EDUCAUSE Review (June 10, 2020), <https://er.educause.edu/blogs/2020/7/artificial-intelligence-and-ethical-accountability>.

Validation will demonstrate that AI algorithms and products are responsible and reliable. There is an international programme by IEEE that certifies AI systems meeting principles of transparency, fairness, unbiasedness, accountability, and responsibility.²⁵

4.7. Safeguarding Whistle-blower Rights

Whistle-blower protection is crucial to ensure that employees feel confident in reporting malpractices within tech companies.⁶ Once more, this aspect has been overlooked in NSAI, UNESCO's framework, and even EU's General Data Protection Regulation.

4.8. Regulation Specific to the Sector

As stated earlier, AI is widespread and intersects with various industries such as healthcare, automotive, e-commerce, insurance, and more. Hence, it is important to establish a thorough national strategy for the advancement and implementation of ethical AI. Governments should collaborate with different sectors to create their own regulations and recommendations for the integration and use of AI. This should align with national policy and international standards. This will enable them to effectively and thoroughly address the challenges that AI could pose in their specific industry sectors.

4.9. Addressing Complaints and Resolving Disputes through Arbitration

Preventive measures can only do so much in light of the challenge posed by AI decision-making models. Nevertheless, in case of an unjust prejudice arising from the AI decision-making system leading to violation of an individual's rights or safety, it is essential to establish grievance redressal mechanisms in all technology company branches in India. Moreover, if a company declines to disclose its algorithm and accepts responsibility for any harm caused, individuals should be able to petition an arbitration tribunal led by an industry expert.²⁶

²⁵<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000380455>.

²⁶Mary K Pratt, AI accountability: Who's responsible when AI goes wrong?, (Aug. 19, 2021), <https://www.techtarget.com/searchenterpriseai/feature/AI-accountability-Whos-responsible-when-AI-goes-wrong>.

5. Regulatory Frameworks for Addressing Bias in AI: The EU AI Act to serve as a Model

Regulatory frameworks are essential for addressing bias in AI. The EU AI Act serves as a model for this purpose. AI has the potential to revolutionize various aspects of our lives. Nevertheless, a crucial obstacle is addressing bias within AI systems, which may result in unjust and discriminatory results. The European Union (EU) has positioned itself as a frontrunner in tackling this matter with the introduction of the proposed AI Act, a thorough regulatory framework for AI advancement and implementation.²⁷

5.1. EU AI Act: Addressing Bias in Artificial Intelligence:

The EU AI Act is designed to implement a risk-based strategy for overseeing AI. This is how it tackles bias:

5.1.1. Risk Classification: The Act categorizes AI systems into four risk levels: unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal. Systems in critical infrastructure or law enforcement are subject to more stringent regulations due to their high-risk nature.

5.1.2 Rules about transparency: The law states that developers must share details about the training data, algorithms, and possible biases of high-risk AI systems.

5.1.3. Human Oversight: It is crucial for high-risk AI systems to have well-defined human oversight mechanisms to guarantee accountability and avoid biased decisions.

5.1.4. Data Governance: The focus is on promoting responsible practices in data governance to reduce bias in training data. This may include methods for recognizing and eliminating bias or utilising a variety of datasets.

The EU AI Act also supports ethical AI development by encouraging developers to embrace fairness-aware design principles. This involves integrating fairness metrics into the development process and investigating methods for creating AI algorithms that are inherently less biased.²⁸

²⁷Regulatory framework proposal on artificial intelligence, Shaping Europe's digital future (Mar. 24, 2023), <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>.

²⁸'On artificial intelligence, trust is a must, not a nice to have,' one lawmaker said. #AI, World Economic Forum (June 30, 2023), <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2023/06/european-union-ai-act-explained/>.

5.2. Expanding Beyond the EU AI Act: A Worldwide Initiative

The EU AI Act establishes a model for other nations interested in creating rules for AI. Although the Act is centred on the European market, its principles can be a useful reference for establishing strong regulatory frameworks globally.²⁹

5.3. Here are some important factors to keep in mind for countries like India:

5.3.1. Adjusting the Risk Framework: Nations have the flexibility to customize the EU's risk classification system to suit their requirements and preferences.

5.3.2. Expanding upon current regulations: Current sector-specific rules can be revised and customized to tackle challenges unique to AI.

5.3.3. Working together is essential: Global collaboration is essential for establishing consistent standards and promoting ethical AI advancement worldwide.³⁰

Addressing bias in AI calls for a comprehensive strategy. The EU AI Act is a great example for other countries to create strong regulatory frameworks. Through a combination of rules and ethical growth strategies, we can guarantee that AI benefits society by encouraging equality, openness, and consideration for human rights.³¹

Conclusion:

Artificial intelligence (AI) holds the potential to bring about significant advancements in various fields, such as healthcare and daily activities. Nevertheless, a concealed danger lies within –

²⁹Sudeep Srivastava, EU AI Act: A Guide to Navigating AI Regulation in Europe, (Feb. 12, 2024), <https://appinventiv.com/blog/ai-regulation-and-compliance-in-europe/>.

³⁰Heather Gentile, Preparing for the EU AI Act: Getting governance right, IBM Blog (Feb. 8, 2024), <https://www.ibm.com/blog/eu-ai-act>

³¹(Mar. 5, 2024), <https://carnegieendowment.org/2024/03/05/ai-and-product-safety-standards-under-eu-ai-act-pub-91870>.

prejudice. This partiality can seep into AI systems, resulting in unfair outcomes that worsen current disparities and jeopardize basic rights. Dealing with these challenges involves a comprehensive strategy that incorporates strong regulations, ethical development methods, and ongoing monitoring.

A top priority is ensuring fairness in AI development. It all begins with data. It is essential to establish strong data practices such as gathering data from various sources and using methods to detect and eliminate bias from current datasets. Moreover, it is crucial to create AI algorithms that prioritize fairness from the beginning. This includes integrating fairness metrics into the design process and investigating methods for creating algorithms that are naturally less prone to bias. It is crucial to advocate for transparency in AI decision-making processes. Clarifying AI (XAI) methods can assist in comprehending how AI reaches its conclusions, enabling human involvement in case bias is identified.

Secondly, promoting teamwork and building public confidence is crucial. Working together among policymakers, developers, researchers, and civil society is crucial for effectively addressing bias. It is crucial for developers to carefully think about ethical implications during the design and development process. Researchers have a crucial part to play in creating tools to identify and reduce bias, while policymakers can set up clear ethical guidelines and regulatory frameworks. It is essential to inform the public about the capabilities and limitations of AI to establish trust and promote responsible use of this technology. Having discussions about AI and its effects on society is crucial to address the ethical challenges at hand.³²

Furthermore, ongoing monitoring and enhancement are essential. Creating systems for continuous monitoring of AI systems in real-world deployment is essential. This enables the identification and reduction of emerging bias problems before they lead to substantial damage. It is crucial to promote ongoing research and development in the realm of fair and ethical AI. As technology advances, it is crucial to keep up with responsible practices. It is crucial to continue discussing AI and its effects on society openly. By promoting a culture of openness and responsibility, we can guarantee that AI benefits humanity, rather than the opposite.

³²Author Raso, Artificial Intelligence & Human Rights: Opportunities & Risks, <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/38021439>.

Ultimately, AI has the potential to greatly influence the course of our future. Nevertheless, it is crucial to address the potential for bias in AI systems through a proactive and collaborative strategy. Through strong regulations, ethical development practices, and ongoing vigilance, we can create AI systems that prioritise fairness, accountability, and transparency. Only when AI reaches its full potential can it truly become a tool for progress, inclusivity, and a brighter future for all. Advancing involves dedicating to creating a fair future, where AI enhances inclusivity and ensures that the advantages of this impactful technology reach everyone in society.

Suggestions:

- Establish strong data collection practices to guarantee that the data is varied and reflects the population the AI system will engage with.
- Set up precise data governance frameworks that emphasize equity and openness in data collection, storage, and usage.
- Create systems for continuous monitoring of AI systems in real-world use to detect and resolve emerging bias problems.
- Encourage public understanding and education on AI capabilities and limitations to foster trust and promote responsible use.

By following these recommendations, we can address the issues of AI bias and discrimination, guaranteeing that AI functions positively, supporting fairness, inclusivity, and a more just future.